

Scientists' Coalition declaration on the One Health impacts of plastics

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The Scientists' Coalition for an Effective Plastics Treaty is a group of nearly 500 independent scientists from more than 70 countries, including countries from the Global South, studying plastics across a wide range of disciplines and geographic perspectives. We have a robust conflict-of-interest policy and processes to ensure our independence and the quality of our outputs.

We strive to transparently communicate the best available, peer-reviewed science to negotiators and delegates in the Global Plastics Treaty negotiations, in order to support evidence-based decision making.

Plastic pollution not only contaminates our planet from the poles to the equator and from the deepest ocean to the highest mountains, but also threatens human, animal and ecosystem health. Plastic pollution occurs along the entire life cycle of plastics, including during polymer and chemical production, plastic use, and disposal.

Plastic pollution includes large debris and small particles— micro- and nanoplastics—which contain polymers and chemicals such as additives and adsorbed contaminants. Plastic debris can also be colonised by microorganisms enabling the spread of antimicrobial resistance and pathogens. Greenhouse gas emissions occur at every stage of the life cycle of plastics. Data from 2015 estimated that plastics were responsible for around 4.5% of global greenhouse gas emissions, and the global carbon footprint is expected to increase in line with the production of plastics.

Over the last decades, scientific research has shown that **plastic pollution occurs across the full life cycle of plastics and plays a central role in the global health burden** with harmful effects on human, animal, and ecosystem health. Microplastics are now present in the food we eat, the water we drink, and the air we breathe. Documented human health impacts of global plastic pollution include an increased risk of cancer, neuropsychiatric disorders, cardiovascular, respiratory and digestive diseases as well as metabolism disruption. Very similar effects can be observed in animals. A recent study estimates that, in a business-as-usual scenario, the number of years of healthy human life lost globally as a result of emissions from plastics could double in 2040 compared to 2016, with a cumulative 83 million years of healthy human life lost as a result of plastics produced and discarded during this period. Primary plastic production accounts for 63% of these health impacts.

Plastics therefore pose multiple, interlinked, and cascading threats to human, animal, and ecosystem health **at the heart of the One Health concept**.

Plastic pollution has huge financial consequences for local economies. Societal and human health costs related to the life cycle of plastics have been evaluated through healthcare expenditure, productivity losses, reduced life expectancy, and diminished quality of life. An estimate of the global health-related costs of a limited number of chemicals used in plastics was found to be around USD 1.5 trillion per year in 2015, which is on par with the costs of climate change. As this estimate was based on only a small subset of plastic chemicals and health outcomes, it is likely to represent an underestimated approximation of the true global health burden of plastics. Furthermore, it leaves aside the costs associated with the

damages caused by plastics to ecosystem health and animal health and other social impacts of plastics on local communities, for example through elevated flooding risks. Plastic pollution negatively affects agriculture and fisheries compromising food production, and the health of farmed and wild animals. **These impacts exacerbate social and geographic inequities** and disproportionately affect already vulnerable and highly exposed populations — particularly women, youth and children, frontline and fenceline communities, waste pickers, Indigenous peoples and local communities, and populations in low income communities and countries.

To protect human, animal, and environmental health, there is **an urgent need to adopt an efficient Global Plastics Treaty to end plastic pollution across the full life cycle of plastics**, as mandated by UNEA Resolution 5/14. Reducing production and consumption is the only effective mean—and the most economically viable lever—to reverse current unsustainable consumption and production levels. This is particularly critical given that the world is already struggling to manage waste at current levels, and that plastic production is expected to triple by 2060. If production trends are not curbed, the sheer volume of plastic entering the system will continue to overwhelm global waste infrastructure, exacerbate pollution, and deepen the economic burden of cleanup and health costs.

Reducing plastic production would strengthen the circular economy, and create favorable market conditions for more sustainable initiatives and generate local social and economic opportunities, while reducing social and geographical inequities. Uncoordinated national measures have been proven to be less effective than harmonised global obligations which provide certainty for businesses. By providing a common playing field for companies, global legally-binding plastic production reduction measures would create opportunities for safe and sustainable innovation. Expanding repair and non plastic reuse systems and diversifying material strategies in all economic sectors —for example in packaging, construction, textiles, and agriculture— support reductions in single-use plastics and reduce overall harmful emissions and impacts. Local supply chains of potentially safer and more sustainable alternative materials (glass, ceramic, natural fibers...) have often been undermined by competition from plastics, whose costs are kept artificially low by fossil fuel subsidies and by the lack of accountability for the costs plastics incur for human, animal, and ecosystem health. Scientific evaluation of alternatives is essential to avoid options that are economically viable but potentially harmful. In addition, simplifying, standardising, and increasing transparency in plastic chemicals and eliminating chemicals of concern in plastics are all crucial to fostering a safer and more effective circular economy. To be efficient, these measures should be guided by evidence-based criteria defined by independent scientists, and aimed towards a just and equitable transition.

Robust science-based measures are urgently needed to effectively phase out the most hazardous, unsustainable, non-essential plastics from the global economy, thereby, significantly reducing global plastic production and plastic pollution and the impacts it incurs. Ultimately, scientific evidence indicates that a global reduction of plastic production and consumption is the most effective lever to protect human, animal, and environmental health. This reduction will drive systematic transformation across sectors and secure a healthier, more sustainable and equitable future.

*Learn more about the Scientists' Coalition: <https://scientistscoalition.org>
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